

Preventing School Hazards: Teachers' Journey on Ensuring a Safe Learning Environment

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Abstract. This phenomenological study explored the discourse of ensuring a safe learning environment for learners by combatting school hazards; specifically, the study aimed to draw significant information from the participants in terms of the personal experiences of their intervention practices in implementing the DRRM practices to determine educational management insights as drawn from the findings of the study that were conducted in Pedro Masanguid Elementary School, Manay South District, Division of Davao Oriental—the experiences of teaching personnel on conducting psychosocial support activities at the start of the new school year. From the participant's responses, the two themes that emerged were the positive experiences that involve developing resilience among learners and opportunities for psychosocial support during the pandemic. The negative experiences involve the changes in skills and resources and post-conflict facilitation readiness on the challenges encountered by the teaching personnel conducting psychosocial support activities at the start of the new school year. Two themes that emerged from the participants' responses were psychosocial intervention resources and the lack of personnel training. The insights gained by the teacher ensured a safe learning environment for the learners. Two themes that emerged from the participant's responses were enhancing DRRM practices and capacitating teachers to facilitate psychosocial support activities, which were beneficial for the learners for the entire school year.

KEY WORDS

1. school hazard 2. journey 3. safe learning environment

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1. Introduction

The most essential function of school teachers is to prevent school hazards for their students and ensure a safe learning environment for them. Children feel better about learning and excel when they feel safe and secure in a classroom environment. The teachers and school officials should learn the importance of creating such an environment and explore what to do when things go wrong. Moreover, safe learning environments provide children with a stress-free space that encourages them to learn and explore. With diligence and care, teachers can create safe classrooms that not only meet the basic needs of young learners but also foster a sense of belonging, encourage curiosity, and support diverse learning styles. In the United States, disasters have ravaged millions of lives. The growth of the population, climate change, and urbanization are the mutilated living conditions for people in communities that are highly at risk

and vulnerable to disasters and infectious diseases. Disasters amalgamated the consequences of poverty and inequity while eroding costly development gains. Eighty-five percent of those exposed to disasters dwelled in developing countries, as stated by The American National Red Cross (2019), Actions taken to prevent the publicity of existence, assets, social and business activities, and commonplace resources from a natural hazard, along with mitigations, are essential to the awareness, education, preparation, and caution systems can reduce the demanding impacts of a natural disaster on groups. Improvement trends in the United States highlight the need to disseminate a new mitigation obligation. In society, advances in hazard and danger assessment are providing decision-makers with progressively accurate and proper instruction on the possible impacts of natural disasters (United et al., 2013). The Department of Education ensures that the health, safety, and well-being of the learners, teachers, and personnel remain our utmost priority. DepEd said that under “managing school operations,” schools “need to receive support from community stakeholders, emphasizing the shared responsibility framework. Schools must conduct simulation activities among school personnel regarding managing the conduct of face-to-face classes, and the school must ensure that learners who will participate in the expansion must submit their parents’ consent. Meanwhile, the main indicator of a school’s readiness under “teaching and learning” is the sufficient supply of learning resources needed in the expansion and class programs that cater to students both in face-to-face arrangements and alternative delivery modes (Gonzales, 2022). The Philippines is one of the top countries in the world at risk of climate-related disasters. The Philippines is a country with a high vulnerability to natural hazards. According to the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (2014), the Philippines ranked third out of 173 countries vulnerable to disaster risks. This assessment was based on the potential of a natural hazard to induce damage to infrastructures and properties, cause enormous human casualties, and cause a decline in mortal welfare, such as livelihoods and health status (Tuladhar et al., 2015). The country is also vulnerable to the effects of climate change and the impact of disaster risks (World Bank, 2014). The Philippines’ geographical location is one factor in why it is a disaster-prone country (Llanto, 2011). Due to its archipelago’s location in the Pacific Ring of Fire, the country is prone to geological and natural disasters such as earthquakes and volcanic eruptions (Blanco, 2015). The country’s location is also highly vulnerable to numerous meteorological hazards. (Lapidez et al., 2015). Some of the schools in the Davao Region are conducting a Disaster Preparedness Activity to help each student on what to do in terms of upcoming calamities. According to Mac Mamon (2017), the Department of Education (DepEd) implements one of the contingencies of the Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act of 2010 (DRRM Act) to promote this activity preparedness in the school curriculums and any other school programs and to boost the level of resiliency of the students toward natural disasters. The City Government of Davao established Central 911 in 2004 to perform the mitigation process needed for the city. They built 911 buildings and bought vehicles to fulfill the readiness against suburban hazards. Furthermore, the City was recognized as the best government emergency management system (Sunstar Davao, 2018). Considering the importance of the safety of learners and school personnel and the need for intensive planning and implementation of DRRM practices, this study must be given the utmost priority. With the implementation of the in-person classes, the learning environment of the learners is one of its priorities. In ensuring a safe learning environment for the learners, the teachers and stakeholders go hand in hand in order to facilitate

the health and safety of everyone, including the community. The researcher found it relevant to look into teachers' experiences in supporting the schools' DRRM practices as they open again after the global health crisis.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This phenomenological study aimed to explore the discourse of ensuring a safe learning environment for learners by combatting school hazards. Specifically, the study aimed to draw significant information from the participants in terms of their personal experiences of their intervention practices and their coping mechanisms in implementing the DRRM practices to determine educational management insights, as drawn from the findings of the study that was conducted in Pedro Masanguid Elementary School, Manay South District, Division of Davao Oriental.

1.2. Research Questions—

- (1) What are teachers' experiences in assuring a safe learning environment?
- (2) What challenges are the teachers encountering in assuring a safe learning environment for the learners?
- (3) What insights are drawn from the experiences and challenges of teachers in assuring a safe learning environment for the learners?

1.3. Definition of Terms—The following terms were operationally essential in the course of the study. A safe learning environment is an educational setting where students feel physically, emotionally, and psychologically secure. It promotes a sense of belonging, respect, and support for all individuals involved in the learning process, including students, teachers, and staff.

1.4. Significant of the Study—The following persons or agencies may be the beneficiaries to determine the outcomes of this study and to whom the findings may be addressed. Department of Education. The DepEd, particularly the District of Manay South, Davao Oriental, may investigate better ways to implement DRRM practices as the learners return to school. Based on the narratives and findings of this study, the stakeholders may be able to adjust to the in-person classes to ensure a safe learning environment.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This research's main and leading theory was the Theory of Planned Behavior and Disaster Preparedness, which was authored by Najafi et al. (2017). The Theory of Planned Behavior and Disaster Preparedness states that disaster readiness, outlined as actions, guarantees the resources necessary to hold out an efficient response. They were offered before a disaster or obtained promptly once required. The preparation and changes were also executed, such as storing food and water, getting ready for a unit emergency setup, setting up an associate degree emergency kit, and doing alternative activities that alleviate risk and injury. Disaster preparedness needs a radical understanding of the factors that influence the performance or carelessness of disaster readiness behaviors. Another equally important theory was the Vested interest theory and Disaster Preparedness, which was proffered by Miller et al. (2013). It articulated the awareness relevance to disaster preparedness and the typical preparedness behaviors in every disaster. The Vested interest theory and Disaster Preparedness

also discuss the importance of managing hazards to gain a better understanding. This theory presents a lesson on what should be done before, during, and after the disaster. This theory also explains the importance of awareness and engaged preparedness and is always informed by making an emergency plan earlier, individually or with other people involved. Therefore, the Vested interest theory and Disaster Preparedness state that being prepared is critical for all possible risks in a disaster, as teachers are responsible for shaping young minds. Part of that responsibility is setting a daily tone for your students that makes them feel safe and comfortable so they can focus on learning. A safe learning environment goes beyond the classroom; the intangible space supports your students in pursuing knowledge, inspires curiosity, and makes them feel empowered to participate in class discussions. Creating this kind of safe learning environment in the classroom is essential for serving the vast spectrum of student learning styles. Ugur(2023) stressed that teachers play a vital role in creating this environment by promoting inclusivity, encouraging open dialogue, and promptly addressing bullying or discrimi-

nation. A safe learning environment values diversity and provides equal opportunities for all students to participate and succeed. It cultivates a sense of belonging, trust, and mutual respect, enabling students to fully engage in their educational journey and reach their fullest potential. Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study. It shows three interconnected working themes. The experiences of teachers in assuring a safe learning environment, a qualitative inquiry that allows researchers and teachers as well as learners to provide the necessary skills, knowledge, and focus on engaging in meaningful inquiry about their professional practice or function would enhance this practice and effect positive changes concerning the educative goals of the learning community. There was a real concern, as could be viewed with the first circle, which interlinks to the second circle: Challenges the teachers encounter in assuring a safe learning environment for the learners. However, the center of the two circles determines that insights were drawn from the experiences of teachers' challenges in ensuring a safe learning environment for the learners, which is critical to school success.

2. Methodology

This chapter presents the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. As elaborated in this chapter, exploring facts and knowledge in this study necessitates the consequent design and implementation.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption was a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret data in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used to reach conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. Good research begins with the selection of the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Stanage (1987) traces 'paradigm

'back to its Greek (paradigm) and Latin origins (paradigm), meaning pattern, model, or example among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions are taken. Differently stated, a paradigm was an action of submitting to a view. This view was supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000), who defend a research paradigm as a "basic set of beliefs that guide action," dealing with first principles, "ultimates, or the researcher's

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

worldview or philosophy. Ontology. This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. Creswell (2012), stated that reality was subjective and multiple, as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the participants discussed the teachers' experiences in assuring a safe learning environment, and their strategies for addressing the challenges and educational insights were examined. In this study, the researcher relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The participant's answers to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of

responses. The participants' responses were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progressed. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln, as cited by Creswell (2012), state that the researcher attempted to lessen the distance between himself or herself and the participants on the epistemological assumption. He suggests that, as a researcher, he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an 'insider.' Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2011). The researcher identified phenomenology with the use of thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers "hold explicit belief." The intention of this study was to gather information from the participants or teachers in Manay South District as to how

they implement DRRM practices based on the guidelines set by DepEd and the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF). It is assumed that close interaction with the participants was established to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry, particularly on the experiences and strategies used in eliminating school hazards and disaster preparedness. Axiology. It refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2012) averred that the role of values in a study was significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes their interpretation in conjunction with participants' interpretation. The researcher ensured the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The

researcher understands the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. Therefore, the researcher preserved the merit of the participants' answers and carefully interpreted the answers in the light of the participants' interpretation. Rhetoric means reporting reality through the eyes of the research participants. This was important because it meant that the research would report objectively on what was observed and heard from the participants. The research used personal voice, qualitative terms, and limited definitions. In the study context, the researcher used the first person to elucidate teachers' experiences as they practice eliminating school hazards and disaster preparedness.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—The methodology was different from the method. Methodology was defined as a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study, the challenges experienced by the elementary school teachers in assuring a safe learning environment in Manay South District were gathered through an in-depth interview (IDI), and their coping mechanisms were extracted from the participants. The researcher's drive to know the deeper meaning of the challenges experienced by elementary school teachers in assuring a safe learning environment became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means by which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias, (2013) considered helpful in looking for "meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena." Using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the challenges experienced elementary school teachers in assuring a safe learning environment in a manner that, as David

(2005) wrote, the themes, symbols, and meaning of the experiences presented. Phenomenological research was based on two premises. The first was that experience was a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge. According to Becker (1992), as cited in Morrissey Higgs (2006), experience is a source of knowledge that shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge. We can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By using phenomenology, which is concerned with the "what" and the "how" (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher projected that the challenges experienced and mechanisms used by the elementary school teachers were explored, and insights were drawn as the basis for possible future research and policy analysis in relation to this research.

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—This study employed a qualitative approach to research, specifically a phenomenological research design. According to Creswell (2012), phenomenology is an approach to qualitative research that focuses on the commonality of lived experiences within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach was to arrive at a description of the nature of the particular phenomenon. Typically, interviews were conducted with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, were also used. The data were read and reread and were culled for phrases and themes grouped into clusters of meanings. Through this process, the researcher could construct the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrive at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. Moreover, Maxwell (2013) also added that with its roots in philosophy, psychology, and education, phenomenology attempts to extract the purest, untainted data, and some interpretations of the approach, bracketing was used by the researcher to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or herself from the process. One method of bracketing is taking notes. According to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design was a qualitative type of research for which interviews provide an in-depth method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help grasp the subjects' perspective. Creswell (2012) also claimed that interviews were primarily done in qualitative research and occur when researchers ask one or more participants general, open-ended questions and record their answers. Often, audio tapes were utilized to allow more consistent transcription. Interviews are also useful for following up with individual respondents after questionnaires, such as further investigating their responses. In qualitative research, interviews were used to pursue the meanings of central themes in the world of their subjects. The main task in doing interviews was to understand the meaning of what the interviewees said (McNamara, 1999). Withal, based on the statements of Quad (2016), the researcher transcribed and typed the data into a computer file to analyze it after interviewing. Interviews particularly help uncover the story behind a participant's experiences and pursuing in-depth information about a topic. The researcher collected data, typically via long interviews, from individuals who had experienced the phenomenon under investigation. Next, the data analysis involved triangulation, which extracted significant statements from the transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each statement fell under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied together to make a general description of the experience, both the textural description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced. The researcher incorporated his or her meaning of the experiences here. Finally, the report was written so that readers could better understand the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. The researcher required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects selected for the study were individuals who had actually experienced the phenomenon. The researcher needed to bracket his or her own experiences and observations, which was difficult. The researcher also needed to decide how and when his or her observations would be incorporated into the study. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches were based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity and emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such, they were powerful tools for understanding subjective experience, gaining insights into people's

motivations and actions, and cutting through the cluster of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Since the focus of this study is to explore and assess the teacher experience and feelings towards the school envi-

2.4. Research Participants—Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size than quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for most perceptions. Obtaining most or all of the perceptions would lead to saturation. Saturation occurs when more participants are added to the study, which does not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (1967) recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (1998) recommends five (5) to 25, and Morse (1994) suggests at least six (6). There are no specific rules when determining an appropriate sample size in qualitative research. Quali-

2.5. Ethical Considerations—The ethical considerations are significant in the design of this research study. The researcher needed to consider several ethical issues about the research participants in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations can be specified as one of the most important parts of the research. The researcher needs to adhere to promote the aims of the research imparting authentic knowledge, truth, and prevention of error. Social Value. The research was essential to society. In this study, the social value was focused on the experience of teachers. This study was specifically conducted among the elementary teachers. This study also served as a basis for the higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions from which classroom teachers could benefit. Thus, the social problem that pushes the interest

environment and the perspectives of the seasoned teachers, the researcher will intend to employ the phenomenology type of qualitative method research.

tative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 1990). The participants of this study were Eight (8) teachers from Manay South District, Division of Davao Oriental. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: (1) must be in the service for at least five years; (2) elementary school teacher; and (3) A teacher that implements DRRM practices in eliminating school hazards. The researcher utilized the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2014). It was also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996).

of the researcher is the challenges faced by the teachers in ensuring a safe learning environment for the learners inside the school. Informed Consent. In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation, as cited by McLeod (2009), was adhered to. The invitation to the participants ensured that their participation in the research was completely voluntary and based on understanding adequate information. The recruitment and selection of participants are lodged in the appendices of this study. Gaining the trust and support of research participants was critical to informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007, as cited by Pillerin, 2012). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research pro-

cess. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgment, consent, and an indication of a willingness to participate in the study release. The purpose of the informed consent letter is to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the study's intent, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and anticipate the information the informants were expected to provide. All participants were required to sign and return the consent letter to the researcher before participating in the research. Vulnerability of Research Participants. The participants of this study were capable of answering the research instrument, for they were all professional teachers in public elementary schools. Thus, the researcher assured them that as the researcher, he or she can easily be reached through the contact number and address in case there are some clarifications or questions about the study. Risks, Benefits, and Safety. The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the panel chair or panel members in case they had queries related to the study. Furthermore, if respondents experienced potential discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelling to participate in any manner. Furthermore, the researcher ensured the respondents were safe during the survey and interview. Thus, the questionnaire was distributed in a safe venue and administered at a convenient time. The dominant concern of this study was the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality and the minimization of risk. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of

2002 to ensure that the data cannot be traced back to their real sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed output that was carried out from this study was kept in anonymity. Furthermore, all the issues were considered so there would be no conflict of interest between the researcher and the respondents. Any misleading information and representation of primary data findings in a biased way must be avoided. Justice. The respondents were informed of the researcher's role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were briefed that they had to be fully honest in answering the survey questions and that any type of communication-related to the research should be done with honesty. Similarly, they were informed that they were the ones to benefit first from the study's results. Transparency. The results of the study were accessed by the respondents and heads of the participating schools because the information is available and would be placed on CDs or other storage devices, which can be requested from the researcher. In addition, by learning about the study's results, classroom teachers will be aware of the significance of the study and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each participant was advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process and that they can be requested and allowed to verify their transcript after the interview is carried out. This allowed the participants to amend or remove any information they felt might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to employ the use of pseudonyms and changing names and or non-significant dates in the interest of the protection of the identity of the participant in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that he or she was qualified to conduct the study. The researcher should complete the academic requirements and pass

the comprehensive examination before thesis writing, the last requirement to obtain the master's degree. The researcher should be qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study would reach its completion. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher strived to complete the study successfully in the specified time and was equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee helped enhance the paper by giving the needed suggestions and recommendations. Also, the researcher ensured that he or she had enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, this study was hoped to be completed within the target time. Community Involvement. The researcher showed respect for the respondents' local traditions, cul-

ture, and views in this study. Moreover, this study did not use deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically in recruiting the participants or data collection methods. Furthermore, the researcher expressed great pleasure in the interviewees' wholehearted participation in the study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher. The researcher respected other works by properly citing the author and rewriting what someone else has said his or her way. The researcher also used quotes to indicate that the text had been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher assured that honesty was present when working on the manuscript and that no intentional misrepresentation and making up of data or results was included or that conclusions were purposefully put forward that were not accurate.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—The researcher is responsible for uncovering, transferring, and exploiting knowledge to benefit educational institutions. To do so, the researcher takes up the following roles in the course of the study: Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research. The researcher interviews the participants and guides them in the process. The researcher interprets ideas and responses based on existing literature and related studies and not on the researcher's knowledge, thoughts, and feelings to avoid the intrusion of bias. Expert in qualitative methods. The researcher implements the qualitative method correctly. To do so, the researcher assesses himself and seeks help from the research adviser and other professionals. These help him demonstrate competence in explaining the study without biasing the participants, conducting interviews according to the design, making appropriate field observations, selecting appropriate artifacts, images, and journal portions, and employing Environmental Triangulation and Thematic Content Analysis precisely. Collector and Keeper

of data. The researcher ensures different ways of making a record of what is said and done during the interview and Focus Group Discussion, such as taking handwritten notes or audio and/or video recording. The recordings are transcribed verbatim before data analysis can begin. Records done by the researcher are properly secured as they contain sensitive information and are relevant to the research. However, the data are being collected, and the researcher's primary responsibility is to safeguard participants and their data. Mechanisms for such safeguarding must be clearly articulated to participants and approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research begins. Data analyst. The researcher sees the phenomenon or problem from the participants' perspective by interpreting data, transcribing and checking, reading between the lines, coding, and theming. The researcher ensures that the findings are true to the participants and their voices are heard. The researcher organizes and presents data. The researcher presents the problem and the related literature and studies that support it.

The study's findings are presented through research questions, stating the results for each one by using themes to show how the research questions were answered in the study. Moreover,

2.7. Data Collection—The following was the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Securing endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School. The researcher asked for an endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School of Rizal Memorial Colleges as one of the documents needed for submission to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent in asking permission to conduct the study. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. On January 2023, the researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study in the identified school. The researcher sent a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent with the attached Chapters 1 and 2 together with the research instrument, which explained the study's objectives and the participants' identification. The researcher waited for the SDS's response before conducting the study. Asking permission from the school heads. After securing the approval of the SDS, the researcher sent letters to the principals of the schools explaining the study to be conducted in their schools. Obtaining consent from the participants. In January 2023, the researcher asked permission from the participants and their parents/guardians. They were formally oriented

2.8. Data Analysis—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered data. The researcher analyzed the answers of the participants from the conducted interviews using Creswell's Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2012), themes in qualitative research are similar codes aggregated together to form a

the researcher gives future directions and implications of the study for improving educational policy and practices.

about the study and the process they would undergo as participants. Conducting the interview. In February 2023, the researcher conducted an in-depth interview using the interview questionnaire. The participants' profiles were taken, notes were jotted down, and conversations were recorded using a sound recorder for easy transcription. The researcher carefully listened and responded actively during the interviews. They were transcribing the responses of the interviewees. The researcher transcribed the interviewees' responses precisely by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since the participants used their vernacular language, the researcher translated it into English language. Data Coding and Thematic Content Analysis. After the transcription, the data will then be categorized and coded. Then, themes were extracted, and individual participant data were compared and contrasted. The researcher then conducted a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needed further explanation and input from the participants; additional information gathered was examined thoroughly and integrated into the existing body of data. After this, data were compared and contrasted between the participants to develop patterns and trends.

major idea in the database. Familiarization with the data was common to all forms of qualitative analysis; the researcher immersed herself in and became intimately familiar with their data, reading and re-reading it and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding was also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis, involving generating pithy labels for

important features of the data relevant to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding was not simply a data reduction method but also an analytic process, so codes capture both a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. The researcher coded every data item and ended this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes was a coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. The researcher ended this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. Reviewing themes. The researcher reflected on whether the themes tell a convincing and compelling story about the data, and began to define the nature of each theme and the relationship between the themes. Thematic Content Analysis was employed by the researcher for these. Thematic Content Analysis was a descriptive presentation of qualitative data in which a detailed analysis of each theme was made by identifying the 'essence' of each theme and constructing a concise, punchy, and informative name for each theme (Andersen, 2013). In addition, to enhance validity and to create a more in-depth picture of the phenomenon, Environmental Tri-

angulation was also employed by the researcher. It was a technique to analyze the same study's results using different data collection methods. The key was identifying which environmental factors might influence the information received during the study. These environmental factors are changed to see if the findings are the same across the settings (David, 2015). This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations, and other factors such as time, day, and season in which the study occurred. The idea was to determine which factors influence the information received; these factors are then changed to see if the findings are the same. Validity can be established if the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental factors (Naeem, Saira, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirement, as mentioned, was the use of environmental triangulation best suited to the environment of the research being conducted. Writing-up involves weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data and contextualizing it about existing literature.

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—The framework analysis of this research was flexible to allow the researcher to either collect all the data and then analyze it or do data analysis during the collection process. The gathered data was sifted, charted, and sorted in the analysis stage under key issues and themes. This involves a five-step process: (1) familiarization, (2) identifying a thematic framework, (3) indexing, (4) charting, and (5) mapping and interpretation (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Familiarization refers to the process during which the researcher becomes familiarized with the transcripts of the data collected (i.e., interview or focus group transcripts, observation, or field notes) and gains an overview of the collected data (Ritchie Spencer,

1994). In other words, the researcher becomes immersed in the data by listening to audiotapes, studying the field, or reading the transcripts. Throughout this process, the researcher was aware of key ideas and recurrent themes and noted them. Due to the sheer volume of data that can be collected in qualitative research, the researcher may be unable to review all of the material. Thus, a selection of the data set would be utilized. The selection would depend on several aspects of the data collection process. For example, the mix of methods used (e.g., interviews, documents, observations), The second stage, identifying a thematic framework, occurs after familiarization, when the researcher recognizes emerging themes or issues in the data

set. These emerging themes or issues may have arisen from a priori themes; however, at this stage, the researcher must allow the data to dictate the themes and issues. The researcher uses the notes taken during the familiarization stage to achieve this. The key issues, concepts, and themes expressed by the participants now form the basis of a thematic framework that can filter and classify the data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Indexing means identifying portions or sections of the data that correspond to a particular theme. This process was applied to all the textual data that has been gathered (e.g., transcripts of interviews). For convenience, Ritchie and Spencer recommend that a numerical system be used to index references and annotate them in the margin beside the text (1994). Qualitative data analysis tools were ideal for such a task. The final stage, mapping and interpretation, involves

the analysis of the key characteristics as laid out in the charts. This analysis should be able to provide a schematic diagram of the event/phenomenon, thus guiding the researcher in their interpretation of the data set. At this point, the researcher was cognizant of the objectives of qualitative analysis: "defining concepts, mapping range and nature of phenomena, creating typologies, finding associations, providing explanations, and developing strategies" (Ritchie Spencer, 1994,). Once again, these concepts, technologies, and associations reflect the participant. Therefore, any strategy or recommendations made by the researcher echo the participants' actual attitudes, beliefs, and values. Figure 2 shows the steps in the study's analytical framework, which involves familiarization, coding, developing a thematic framework, indexing, charting, mapping, and interpretation.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—Trustworthiness was all about establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability. In the qualitative study, trustworthiness was very important because its results and findings would depend on how the researcher conducted it. The trustworthiness of a research study is important for evaluating its worth. Due to the nature of the qualitative study, honesty in all the data and details is required. Trustworthiness makes the researcher's study worthy to read, share, and be proud of. Credibility measured how confident the qualitative researcher was in the truth of the research study's findings. The researcher in this study believed that honesty in everything you do is essential to attaining worthwhile success. The researcher has no derogatory records or administrative issues that ruin her integrity. Lincoln and Guba (2000) state that credibility refers to the idea of internal consistency, where the main issue is "how we ensure rigor in the research process and how we communicate to others that we have done so." Transferabil-

ity was how the qualitative researcher demonstrated that the research study's findings were applicable to other contexts. In this case, "other contexts" can mean similar situations, similar populations, and similar phenomena. The researcher has already studied the effects of using a graphic organizer as a strategy for teaching reading comprehension. Using graphic organizers as a strategy in teaching reading comprehension is effective in the domains of analysis and creation. With this, the researcher was interested to know the students' perspective of using this strategy. Gasson (2004) emphasizes transferability as the extent to which the reader can provide a generalization of the study based on his context and can address the core issue of "how far a researcher may make claims for a general application of the theory." Confirmability was the degree of neutrality in the research study's findings. In other words, this means that the findings are based on participants' responses and not the researcher's potential bias or personal motivations. This involves ensuring

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

that researcher bias does not skew the interpretation of what the research participants said to fit a certain narrative. The information using the audit trail in this situation is thoughtfully recorded by the researcher, which highlights every step of data analysis that was made in order to provide a rationale for the decisions made. This helps establish that the research study's findings accurately portray participants' responses. Gasson (2004) states that confirmability was based on the acknowledgment that research is never objective. Dependability was the extent to which other researchers could repeat the study and that the findings would be consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate your study, they should have enough

information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. A qualitative researcher uses an inquiry audit to establish dependability, which requires an outside person to review and examine the research process and the data analysis to ensure that the findings are consistent and can be repeated. In this component, a database was very important in backing up information collected and noting changes for all research studies. All the data collected was properly kept for future use as references. Gasson (2004) stated that dependability deals with the core issue of "how a study was conducted should be consistent across time, researchers, and analysis techniques."

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from analyzing the interview data. It presents themes that emerge from the analysis, along with comprehensive discussions that answer the study's objectives. This chapter discussed the themes that emerged from the data gathered. The result primarily presents the description and background of the participants assigned pseudonyms to conceal their identities.

3.1. Experiences of Teachers in Assuring a Safe Learning Environment—The participants have extensive experience assuring a safe learning environment. The themes are divided into positive and negative experiences to categorize the direction in which the participants presented

their responses. The role of teachers in disaster management and psychosocial support in reopening schools were the participants' positive experiences. Meanwhile, disaster preparedness in schools and limited training or support are among the negative experiences they encountered.

3.1.1. Positive Experiences: The Role of Teachers in Disaster Management—Teachers play a critical role in ensuring the safety of learners in schools. They actively engage in various experiences and practices to create a safe and secure learning environment. The teachers take on this role and face additional workloads. The participants realized its importance for their learners, so they did it diligently.

are of great importance in educational planning. Teachers, as human sources, play an important role in educational planning, and their knowledge and skills should be evaluated regularly. (Chondekar, 2018). The participants also expressed the importance of their roles in the individual interviews. The global pandemic has highlighted the role of teachers in disaster management for the sake of their learners. Teachers and media play a prominent role in efficient disaster management systems, which is vital for a

Teachers play a crucial role in class, especially in disaster education. Human resources

suitable future of life on earth. That is the significance of a holistic approach to disaster management. Isolated thoughts, preparation, awareness programs, attitudes, and other activities should be co-operatively integrated with the participation of all sections of the community, for the community, and by the community. Educational institutions, mostly schools and teacher education institutions, are the most effective sources for inculcating awareness by educating students about disaster management. (Chondekar, 2018). In response to this, the participants experienced the intensification of their roles as the pandemic hit. School safety and educational continuity require a dynamic, continuous process initiated by management involving workers, students, parents, and the local community. School disaster management involves the following steps: assess hazards, vulnerabilities, capacities, and resources; plan and implement for physical risk reduction; maintain safe facilities, standard operating procedures, and training for disaster re-

3.1.2. Psychosocial Support in Reopening of Schools—Psychosocial support activities are designed to encourage children to establish healthy routines and help them connect with their peers. While there are various ways to provide psychosocial support, conducting recreational and educational activities such as arts and crafts, storytelling, playing games, singing, musical instruments, and dance classes might be incorporated during classes, especially for younger students. This is one of the participants' positive experiences because they consider psychosocial support relevant, especially after the 2-year school closure. Other participants shared that psychosocial support is an opportunity for them to help their learners cope with their mental health. Psychosocial support focuses on the aspects of an environment or situation that impact affected populations' social and psychological well-being. While psychosocial support can be achieved via specific targeted activities

and skills regularly, with realistic simulation drills. (Malaviya, 2014). In Japan, teachers, whose role is to continue educating children, also managed the evacuation centers. It has been reported that teachers managed the centers and took charge of evacuation center operations because of the confusion at the centers. It was extremely difficult for the school teachers to be involved with children after the disaster. The experiences were published for the future as those of a teacher rather than in an English-language article. Managing temporary shelters was time-consuming. To make the most of the lessons learned, mechanisms were created to enable cooperation among teachers with the aim of post-disaster restoration of educational activities in 2002. From that time, efforts began to foster teaching staff with expertise in areas such as disaster preparedness and evacuation center operation and the ability to respond to integrate disaster management practically.

and programs, it is important to understand that all interactions with children have the potential to be psychosocially supportive. Psychosocial support activities are designed to encourage children to establish healthy routines and help them connect with their peers. While there are various ways to provide psychosocial support, conducting recreational and educational activities such as arts and crafts, storytelling, playing games, singing, musical instruments, and dance classes might be incorporated during classes, especially for younger students. The participants added that they lack this as a service to their learners. Psychosocial support focuses on the aspects of an environment or situation that impact the social and psychological well-being of affected populations. While psychosocial support can be achieved via specific targeted activities and programs, it is important to understand that all interactions with children have the potential to be psychosocially supportive.

This message must be spread to all humanitarian workers involved in the relief effort, even if they do not have primary responsibility for child welfare. All humanitarian actors are responsible for ensuring that beneficiaries' emotional well-being is respected in humanitarian operations. For example, respecting children, showing a positive attitude towards them, and valuing their presence are all ways of helping improve children's self-confidence, self-esteem, and well-being. (Papyrus, 2018). Another part of mental health and psychosocial support is to bridge the gap between people and their families. In addition, it hopes to help individuals deal with their problems effectively in order to

alleviate the stress and suffering they are experiencing. Having a support system can save one's day. That's why mental health and psychosocial support is now given the spotlight it deserves. Different organizations work together to help children exposed to conflicts, calamities, and crises. This is a significant move to guiding children to the path where they can avoid suffering from psychological problems. Without the psychosocial support they need, they could experience long-term effects. These afflictions can cause anxiety disorder, depression, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD); and if not treated, children can carry these effects until they are old (Philippines, 2021).

3.1.3. Negative Experiences: Disaster Preparedness in Schools—Disaster preparedness addresses the means conducted to reduce and prepare for the outcomes of disasters via forecasting the possibilities, avoiding disasters and dangers that could be brought forth, mitigating and minimizing the aftermath on highly risked locations and populations that are vulnerable, and responding effectively on dealing and surviving its consequences. However, the participant's account views the preparations as insufficient, which was highlighted by the global pandemic. The unexpected health crisis proves that the disaster preparedness practices do not cover all the calamities that may hit. Its pursuit of risk reduction programs results in rescuing more lives and livelihoods upon disasters and empowering the distressed population to attain normalcy within a short period. However, it must also be kept in mind that a continually integrated procedure is needed to ensure and develop a massive range of risk reduction programs. Thus, it necessitates contributing several factors, like healthcare, logistics, training, livelihood, recovery, and institutional development. Unfortunately, the participants shared that the disaster management practices in their schools are limited to earthquake and fire drills only.

There are a lot of natural disasters that schools do not prepare for. The impacts of disaster are in the area of physical, educational, economic as well as psychological. The slogan for the UN International Strategy for Disaster Reductions (2006) global campaign, "Disaster Reduction Begins at School," is accurate and pertinent. Basic education and disaster prevention go hand in hand. The methods for recognizing and assessing the future impact of hazards, vulnerabilities, and risks and identifying strengths and capacities contain the fundamentals of scientific thinking and the basics of good citizenship and participatory governance. The participants feel that the school should prepare for what lies ahead. The values, attitudes, and technologies needed for physical protection, informed planning, environmental stewardship, disaster-resilient design, and construction are the same as those fundamental to sustainable development and livelihood security. The skills and provisions for disaster response are empowering and confer safety in everyday life. Disaster resiliency is built upon a foundation of analytical and problem-solving skills and draws from the development of personal and interpersonal intelligence (Petal, 2008) According to Aquino et al. (2014), climate change is humanity's most

crucial and prevalent threat. The Intergovernmental Panel, the highest scientific body responsible for assessing climate change risk, declared that the earth's surface warming is unambigu-

3.1.4. Limited training or support—Demographic and cultural factors, personal experiences, and attitudes may influence disaster prevention awareness. Many teachers have not previously experienced a disaster. Therefore, teachers need education to raise awareness of disaster prevention. Some teachers may lack proper training or support in handling safety-related situations, such as managing emergencies or dealing with aggressive behavior, which can impact their ability to ensure the safety of learners. Participant 5 shared that there are a lot of aspects of DRRM that they need training on. Further, the education for disaster prevention awareness includes various measures, such as disaster education awareness and even disaster recovery awareness. Education to raise disaster awareness is valuable for risk reduction and disaster preparedness. Due to the vagueness of the definition of disaster prevention awareness, the impact of education was not systematically assessed. It is important to identify factors that may improve disaster prevention awareness to promote it specifically. The participants shared that disaster management training is limited. Preventing the disruption of schooling requires not only the development of teaching staff with disaster preparedness skills but also a commitment by public institutions to reduce the disaster risks to people, their livelihoods, social and economic infrastructure, and environmental resources. Moreover, it requires these institutions to participate with the general public at all implementation stages in building strong communities in the face of disasters. Because schools are the center of communities, they can contribute to building communities that can cope well with disasters. (Yamasaki,

If unconstrained, the impacts of climate change on humanity and the environment are unparalleled and will steadily affect the lives of future generations.

2020). The concept of capacity building for managing and reducing disaster risk is highlighted extensively in the Hyogo Framework for Action (2015). The framework emphasizes the need for accelerated efforts to build community- and national-level capacities to manage and reduce risk, and it links these efforts to all five priority action areas. A key aspect is ensuring that disaster risk reduction is a national and local priority with a strong institutional basis for implementation. This requires building institutional capacity, particularly in developing early warning systems, to provide a sense of security and preparedness. (Yamasaki, 2020). (Corboz, 2019). Education, and especially environmental education in both formal (theory-based) and non-formal, like lectures, campaigns, hands-on experience, experiential learning, and field trip classes, has proved to be a crucial factor of any bottom-up hazard mitigation strategy, especially when recovering from disasters. The environmental education community, particularly educators, has become indispensable in contemporary societies in terms of risk management and natural hazard prevention. These educators use theoretical (school-based) and less formalized approaches to raise awareness of the importance of specific strategies for disaster risk reduction. Their efforts inspire and motivate multiple stakeholders – namely students, other teachers, and citizens- to take an active role in disaster preparedness. (Christina, 2022). It is important to note that while these negative experiences can pose challenges, teachers play a crucial role in addressing them and taking appropriate actions to ensure the safety and well-being of learners to the best of their abilities. Collaboration with school administrators, colleagues, parents, and

Fig. 3. Emerging Themes on the Experiences of Teachers in Assuring a Safe Learning Environment

relevant stakeholders can help mitigate these challenges and promote a safer learning environment. Figure 3 above shows teachers' experiences in assuring a safe learning environment. Two themes emerged from the participants' responses: the positive experiences involving the role of teachers in disaster management and the psychosocial support provided in reopening schools. The negative experiences involved disaster management in schools and limited training and support. These themes imply that the teachers experienced positive experiences, especially in developing resilience, which is very relevant after the pandemic, and it is also an opportunity to provide for the psychosocial sup-

port needs of the learners. It also highlighted the importance of teachers' roles in disaster management, which will directly affect the school community. However, there are also negative experiences that the teachers encountered, especially in the disaster management practices that lack some areas in DRRM that are covered. The schools can only conduct preparations for earthquakes and fires but neglect the other types of natural disasters. Another point is the limited training and support offered to the learners and teachers. It was brought to light that the training provided by the DRRM is lacking, especially in terms of providing mental health and wellness to the learners.

3.2. *Challenges Encountered by the Teachers in Assuring a Safe Learning Environment for*

the Learners—Ensuring a safe learning environment is a crucial responsibility of teachers. They

play a vital role in creating an atmosphere that promotes physical, emotional, and psychological safety for their students. However, achieving this goal is not always easy, and teachers face

3.2.1. Lack of Training on Disaster Preparedness—Disaster preparedness is an essential aspect of ensuring the safety of students and teachers in schools. Capacitating teachers on disaster preparedness can help them to better understand the risks and challenges associated with various types of disasters and develop effective plans to protect themselves and their students in the event of an emergency. However, the participants in the field feel that they are not experts in handling disaster management practices. They felt the need to tap experts to do it. When teachers are equipped with knowledge and skills related to disaster preparedness, they can take appropriate steps to protect themselves and their students in the event of an emergency. This can include implementing evacuation plans, providing first aid, and ensuring students are accounted for and safe. Capacitating teachers on disaster preparedness can increase their confidence in responding to emergencies. This can help reduce anxiety and stress levels and improve overall morale among teachers and students. The training can also help teachers develop the resilience needed to recover from a disaster. This can include developing coping mechanisms, building social support networks, and developing strategies for rebuilding after a disaster. Schools can provide training sessions,

3.2.2. Inadequate Resources Present in the School—Many schools, especially those in rural or low-income areas, may have limited access to resources for DRRM, such as books, training materials, and equipment. This can make it difficult for teachers to teach DRRM effectively. The participants shared that re-

sources are really needed, especially now that they are tasked with handling psychosocial support activities. The quote highlights the need for increased attention and resources towards the domain of post-conflict psychosocial support in DRRM. This could involve providing more training and resources for teachers, school

several challenges. Based on the responses, the challenges that the teachers experienced are capacitating teachers on disaster preparedness and resources to be present in the school. workshops, and other forms of professional development to capacitate teachers on disaster preparedness. Teachers can also be encouraged to participate in community-based disaster preparedness programs to build their knowledge and skills. Schools can also develop and implement disaster preparedness plans involving teachers and other stakeholders to ensure that everyone is prepared for emergencies. This is supported by Lee (2021) when he emphasizes the importance of enhancing disaster preparedness and resilience in schools through teacher training. This means that providing teachers with the skills and knowledge to effectively respond to disasters is critical to ensuring the safety of students and staff in schools. There are various strategies for capacitating teachers on disaster preparedness, such as using interactive training sessions and simulation exercises. Additionally, the importance of collaboration and communication among stakeholders, including teachers, administrators, and emergency responders, is highlighted as critical to developing effective disaster preparedness plans. It also notes the potential role of technology in enhancing disaster preparedness and communication during emergencies, such as using mobile apps and social media to facilitate communication between teachers, parents, and emergency responders.

counselors, and mental health professionals to address the specific needs of learners affected by conflict. It may also involve collaboration with local community organizations and government agencies to provide more comprehensive support to learners and their families. Participant number 2 emphasizes the importance of having resources available, especially when working with young children, who are often more vulnerable and may require specific types of support during a disaster. Resources could include emergency response plans, communication tools, first aid supplies, and materials for teaching disaster preparedness and response. Limited resources pose a significant challenge to integrating DRRM education in the school curriculum. The study found that many schools lacked the necessary resources, such as teaching materials and equipment, to effectively teach DRRM concepts to students. Inadequate teacher training is another significant challenge to integrating DRRM education in the school curriculum. Many teachers felt unprepared to teach DRRM concepts and lacked the necessary knowledge and skills to effectively incorporate these concepts into their lessons. Lack of institutional support was identified as a challenge to integrating DRRM education in the school curriculum. The study found that many schools lacked support from school administrators and government

3.3. Insights Drawn from The Experiences and Challenges of Teachers In Assuring A Safe Learning Environment For The Learners— Teachers' personal experiences and preparedness for emergencies can influence their ability to ensure a safe learning environment. Teachers who have experienced disasters or received

*3.3.1. Capacitating Teachers on Disaster Management Skills—*Capacitating teachers in disaster management involves providing them

agencies, which hindered their ability to The figure above shows the challenges encountered by the teachers in assuring safe learning environment for the learners. Two themes emerged from the responses of the participants which were inadequate resources present in school and lack of training on disaster preparedness. These themes imply that the teachers experienced challenges in conducting DRRM practices in the school. One of the challenges is the need for teachers to build more capacity in DRRM concepts. Disaster preparedness training and resources must be regularly updated and maintained to remain effective. Schools should develop long-term plans to ensure their preparedness efforts remain sustainable. They also experience a challenge with the resources available in school about disaster management. Schools can be better prepared for emergencies, such as natural disasters or other crises, by having the necessary resources and training. This can help ensure the safety of students, staff, and the wider community and effectively teach DRRM concepts (Cruz, 2021). Figure 4 shows the teachers' experiences of challenges encountered in assuring a safe learning environment for the learners. Two themes emerge: lack of training in disaster preparedness and Inadequate Resources Present in the School.

training in emergency response may be better equipped to identify and mitigate risks. Based on the participants' responses, they were able to draw insights into the DRRM practices in their respective schools. These insights are enabling teachers to develop disaster management skills and upgrade DRRM practices in the school.

with the knowledge, skills, and resources necessary to prepare for, respond to, and recover from emergencies or disasters. By providing teachers

Fig. 4. Emerging Themes on the Challenges Encountered by the Teachers in Assuring a Safe Learning Environment for the Learners

with disaster management training, they can become better equipped to respond to emergencies in a timely and effective manner. This can help minimize the impact of disasters on students, staff, and the wider community. When teachers are trained in disaster management, they can help create a safer learning environment for students. They can identify potential hazards and take steps to mitigate them, such as securing loose furniture or ensuring emergency exits are easily accessible. Teachers are often viewed as trusted community leaders. By capacitating them in disaster management, they can help educate and engage the wider community in disaster preparedness efforts. This can help build a culture of safety and resilience. The importance of capacitating teachers in disaster management has become even more apparent after the COVID-19 pandemic. The COVID-19 pandemic has demonstrated the importance of disaster preparedness. By capacitating teachers in disaster management, schools can be better prepared for future emergencies and crises. The pandemic has forced schools to be flexible and

adapt quickly to changing circumstances. Capacitating teachers in disaster management can help them develop the skills to be more agile and adaptable in the face of future crises. In summary, capacitating teachers in disaster management is crucial after the COVID-19 pandemic. It can help schools be better prepared for future emergencies, promote health and hygiene, develop flexibility and adaptability, support mental health, and prepare for future pandemics or health emergencies. It can have significant benefits for schools and their communities. It can improve emergency response, enhance safety, engage the community, reduce anxiety, and be cost-effective. Disasters and emergencies can strike at any time, and the COVID-19 pandemic has demonstrated the importance of disaster preparedness. In the wake of the pandemic, schools must be equipped to respond to future crises effectively. Capacitating teachers in disaster management is crucial to ensure that schools are prepared for future emergencies. In addition, capacitating teachers in disaster management can help schools develop flexibility and adapt-

ability. The pandemic has forced schools to be agile and adaptable in response to changing circumstances. By providing teachers with disaster management training, they can develop the skills to respond effectively to future crises. Moreover, the pandemic has had a significant

impact on the mental health of students and staff. By providing teachers with training on disaster management, they can better support the mental health and well-being of those affected by disasters or emergencies (Perez, 2022).

3.3.2. Upgrading DRRM Practices in the School—Upgrading DRRM practices in schools is essential to ensure the safety and well-being of learners, as well as to mitigate the impact of disasters and emergencies. The participants highlight the importance of recognizing and addressing the psychological impact of conflict on learners, as mental health issues can have long-term effects on their well-being, educational outcomes, and overall development. They suggested that by including mental health in DRRM practices, schools and communities can better support the recovery and resilience of learners affected by conflict. Schools should regularly review and update their DRRM plans to ensure that they reflect the evolving needs of learners. The participants acknowledge the importance of recognizing the impact of disasters on the mental health of learners and addressing their psychosocial needs to promote their recovery and resilience. According to them, an enhanced DRRM plan of action should not only focus on physical safety measures but also prioritize the mental health and well-being of learners. The participant's statement implies that the current Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) practices may not adequately address the global pandemic's needs. As a result, DRRM practices need to be updated to accommodate these new needs. The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the importance of addressing public health emergencies in disaster preparedness plans. The implication is that an updated DRRM plan should take into account the specific challenges and risks posed by the pandemic, including issues related to infec-

tion control, mental health, and social distancing measures. The COVID-19 pandemic has brought unprecedented challenges to the world, affecting every aspect of life, including education, health, and the economy. The pandemic has also highlighted the importance of disaster risk reduction and management (DRRM) practices in preparing for and responding to public health emergencies. DRRM practices are critical in ensuring the safety and well-being of individuals and communities affected by disasters. However, the COVID-19 pandemic has exposed gaps in the current DRRM practices, necessitating an update to accommodate the specific challenges and risks posed by the pandemic. Additionally, the pandemic has highlighted the importance of digital resources in disaster preparedness and response. Schools and communities must have access to digital resources, such as online learning platforms and communication tools, to facilitate remote learning and communication during a pandemic (Gonzales, 2022). The figure above shows the insights drawn from the experiences and challenges teachers face in ensuring a safe learning environment for the learners. Two themes emerged from the responses of the participants: capacitating teachers to develop disaster management skills and upgrading the DRRM practices in the school. This is to ensure a safe learning environment for the learners. The themes that emerged from the participants' responses regarding enhancing DRRM practices and capacitating teachers to facilitate psychosocial support activities have significant implications for education and disaster risk reduction. Firstly, enhancing DRRM

Fig. 5. Emerging Themes on the Insights Drawn from the Experiences and Challenges of Teachers in Assuring a Safe Learning Environment the Learners.

practices is crucial for ensuring the safety and well-being of students and staff in schools. Disasters and emergencies can happen at any time, and schools should be equipped with the knowledge and resources to mitigate the risks and respond effectively. By improving DRRM practices, schools can create a safe learning environment and reduce the potential impact of disasters on students and staff. Secondly, capacitating teachers to facilitate psychosocial support activities is essential for promoting the mental health and well-being of students. Disasters and emergencies can significantly impact the mental health of children, and it is essential to have trained professionals who can provide psychosocial support to those in need. By providing training and support to teachers, schools can en-

sure that students receive the necessary care and attention to cope with the aftermath of disasters and emergencies. These themes highlight the importance of integrating DRRM and psychosocial support into the education system. By doing so, schools can create a safe and supportive learning environment for students, promote resilience, and help them develop the necessary skills to cope with disasters and emergencies in the future. Figure 5 shows insights drawn from teachers' experiences and challenges in assuring a safe learning environment for the learners and the emergence of the two themes: capacitating teachers on disaster management skills and upgrading Disaster Reduction Management (DRRM) practices in the school.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents a brief overview of the study followed by implications based on the findings of the study. Future directions in the field of teachers' experiences are also discussed here. This phenomenological study aims to explore the discourse of ensuring a safe learning environment

for learners by combatting school hazards. It aimed to draw significant information from the participants in terms of the personal experiences of their intervention practices and their coping mechanisms in implementing the DRRM practices to determine educational management insights as drawn from the findings of the study that will be conducted in Pedro Masanguid Elementary School, Manay South District, Division of Davao Oriental.

4.1. Findings—The participants' responses to the experiences of teaching personnel conducting psychosocial support activities at the start of the new school year revealed two themes: the positive experiences that involve developing resilience among learners and opportunities for psychosocial support during the pandemic, and the negative experiences that involve changes in skills and resources and post-conflict facilitation readiness. The participants' responses to the challenges encountered by teaching personnel conducting psychosocial support activities at the start of the new school year revealed two themes: psychosocial intervention resources and the lack of personnel training. The teacher gained insights into ensuring a safe learning environment for the learners. Two themes emerged from the participants' responses: enhancing DRRM practices and capacitating teachers to facilitate psychosocial support activities that would benefit the learners for the entire school year.

4.2. Implications—The generated themes imply that the teachers experienced positive experiences, especially in developing resilience, which was very relevant after the pandemic, and it was also an opportunity to provide for the psychosocial support needs of the learners. These activities focus on the mental health needs of the learners. However, there were also negative experiences that the teachers encountered, especially in the changes they underwent, which involved skills and resources, which also confused them about facilitating it. Another point brought out was the readiness of teachers to facilitate psychosocial activities, which may come as a challenge, and the ineffectiveness of the activities. The teachers experienced challenges in conducting psychosocial support intervention at the start of the school year. One of the challenges was the psychosocial intervention resources that were not readily available to the teachers. These resources should also involve the psychosocial intervention needs of the learners for the rest of the school year. They also experienced a challenge due to the lack of personnel training, which was a big tool in making teachers confident in facilitating psychosocial support intervention for the learners. The teachers felt that mental health was a sensitive aspect of children's lives, and it should be dealt with enough expertise. The participants' responses regarding enhancing DRRM practices and capacitating teachers to facilitate psychosocial support activities have significant implications for education and disaster risk reduction. Firstly, enhancing DRRM practices was crucial for ensuring school students and staff's safety and well-being. Disasters and emergencies can happen anytime, and schools should have the knowledge and resources to mitigate the risks and respond effectively. By improving DRRM practices, schools could create a safe learning environment and reduce the potential impact of disasters on students and staff. Capacitating teachers to facilitate psychosocial support activities is essential for promoting students' mental health and well-being. Disasters and emergencies could significantly impact the mental health of children, and it was essential to have trained professionals who could provide psychosocial support to those in need. By providing training

and support to teachers, schools could ensure that students receive the necessary care and attention to cope with the aftermath of disasters and emergencies. These themes highlight the importance of integrating DRRM and psychosocial support into the education system. By doing so, schools can create a safe and supportive learning environment for students, promote re-

silience, and help them develop the necessary skills to cope with disasters and emergencies in the future. This research would provide an understanding of teachers' experiences in assuring a safe learning environment for the learners. Data obtained had implications for various educational stakeholders, including policymakers, administrators, and teachers.

4.3. Future Directions—Continued research about assuring a safe learning environment in schools should be given more emphasis, especially after the pandemic that hit the world. Continuous professional development may be regularly conducted to ensure teachers have the necessary skills to deliver instruction beyond the classroom corners. The agency must prioritize the professional development of the teachers, especially in providing psychosocial support and intervention for the learners for the rest of the school year. This research may also encourage the improvement of school DRRM practices that should involve teachers' and learners' mental health awareness. The pandemic was a learning experience for everyone, highlighting people's mental wellness, including teachers and learners. Future research on effective psychosocial support intervention should be conducted to make the agency aware of the easiest way to provide mental health activities for our learners in the classroom. The pandemic has brought to the forefront the importance of mental health and well-being. The stress, anxiety, and uncertainty

caused by the pandemic have affected people of all ages, including learners and teachers. Thus, it was essential to prioritize mental wellness in the education system and support those who need it. Policymakers may lead the implementation of an updated DRRM plan of action, which would include the mental wellness of learners after a crisis. This would highlight the psychological needs of learners, and the agency would ensure that learners are of sound body and mind even after experiencing disasters that can hamper educational service delivery. Administrators may provide technical assistance to teachers when adapting new tasks to improve their disaster management skills. With enough support from the school administrator, the teachers can rise above their challenges. Teachers may continue attending professional development activities to acquire a new set of skills required to provide psychosocial support activities and innovations in DRRM practices. With enough skills and motivation, teachers would continue to ensure that learners learn despite the global pandemic's challenges.

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